

Poster presentation**Creating synthetic topography from Cassini RADAR data as an input for mesoscale atmospheric models****L. E. Bonnefoy, M. Lefèvre, A. Spiga, A. Chatain, A. G. Hayes, S. Rodriguez, A. Lucas, V. Poggiali, M. Malaska**

Mesoscale atmospheric modeling of Titan, which is for instance capable of predicting the direction and strength of winds at kilometeric resolution, requires high-resolution topography as an input. Titan's best topography maps (Corlies et al., 2017) consist of a combination of radar altimetry, the SARTopo dataset (Stiles et al., 2009), and SAR stereoradargrammetry. The spatial resolution, vertical uncertainty, and large data gaps in the existing topography do not reflect the expected variations at kilometeric resolution. In the absence of better topography data for the foreseeable future, we propose to use synthetic topography for mesoscale atmospheric modeling.

In order to study (1) the surface atmospheric and sedimentary environment at the Dragonfly landing site and (2) the role of surface liquids in mesoscale atmospheric circulation, we focus on two regions: a 1000-km-wide region centered on the Dragonfly landing site near Selk crater, and a 250-km-wide area in the northern small lakes region. We first create a geomorphological map based on Cassini SAR images, simpler than previous geomorphological maps in order to minimize the number of parameters. Each unit (e.g., dune field, crater rim, or empty lake basin) is then assigned a shape whose parameters (e.g., dune width and height, crater rim height and slope, empty lake basin depth) are inspired from available topography data and from published analyses. Using a similar method, we also create synthetic maps of the surface albedo and aerodynamic roughness length.

We recall that these synthetic maps are neither real nor realistic, as they are greatly simplified and assume that all features within a unit are identical. However, they have the great advantage of being parametrized, which allows us to vary each parameter and test its influence on mesoscale model outputs such as surface winds. Some key questions that we are seeking to answer include: At what height do crater rims and mountains on Titan start to significantly influence surface winds? How much do lake ramparts influence surface circulation? Can topography cause the wind patterns responsible for the dune morphologies observed on Titan, including cross-hatched dunes at the Dragonfly landing site?